

“Administration of Fast Dissolving Oral Thin Film Orlistat drug via sublingual route instead of oral route

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ABSTRACT

Background: Patients with obesity are given orlistat (120) mg capsules three times a day by oral route of administration, although oral method of administration does not produce good and accurate outcomes.

Aim: To see if giving orlistat in tablet form as a sublingual medication delivery mechanism is useful in treating obesity in patients.

Densign and Setting: This article is based on past research and does not include any experiments involving humans or animals undertaken by any of the authors.

Method: We use Google Scholar, Medline, PubMed, Research Gate, and Science Direct to retrieve scientific databases. In this paper, we propose that an orlistat medication be prepared in tablet form and administered sublingually. Orlistat is an anti-obesity medication that is taken by mouth. As a result, our fictitious assumptions. The reason for this is that the anti-obesity Orlistat thin film sublingual formulation is more precise and speedier. Oral orlistat has a delayed beginning of effect. Orlistat is usually taken three times a day, following a fatty meal. Thin films are thought to be a more practical, easy-to-swallow, and quickly-dissolving dose form.

Results: It is our belief that treating obesity with orlistat using a sublingual mode of administration might result in beneficial and improved outcomes.

Conclusion: Oral orlistat has little effect on obese individuals' results. We found that orlistat taken sublingually had a stronger effect against obesity after doing a literature review.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

A. Orlistat Drug

Orlistat is a drug that is taken by mouth. Orlistat (tetrahydrolipstatin) is a prescription diet pill available in the United States. An anti-obesity medicine has been authorized by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). It's really saturated. Streptomyces toxytricini produced an endogenous lipstatin derivative. Orlistat has been authorized by the FDA for the following uses:

- Obese patients with a body mass index (BMI) more than 30 kg/m
- Patients with a body mass index (BMI) more than 27 kg/m and risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes, and dyslipidemia.

Orlistat works best when combined with a healthy diet and regular exercise. Then, within two weeks after starting orlistat, weight loss begins to slow.

B. MECHANISM

Orlistat works by suppressing stomach and pancreatic lipases in a reversible manner. Lipases are enzymes that aid in the breakdown of dietary fats. They function by converting triglycerides into free fatty acids and monoglycerides, which are easily absorbed. Orlistat inactivates lipases by binding to the serine residues of their active areas. The inactivation of lipases hinders the breakdown of triglycerides, preventing the absorption of free fatty acids. Orlistat's main effect is to suppress localized lipase in the intestine. Orlistat's action does not need systemic absorption. It reduces dietary fat absorption by around 30% when taken at the recommended dose.

C. ADMINISTRATION

Orlistat is taken orally three times a day at a dosage of 120 mg/cap. The administration should take place during or shortly after a fat-containing meal. Doses more than 120 mg have not been found to provide any further benefit. The patient should follow a nutritionally balanced, low-calorie diet with fewer than 30% fat calories.

D. PHARMACOKINETICS

a) Absorption

Orlistat works primarily through a local impact in the stomach, with very little systemic exposure.

b) Distribution

The majority of the medication (greater than 99 percent) is bound to plasma proteins (lipoproteins and albumin are the major binding proteins).

c) Metabolism

Orlistat is mostly metabolized within the gut wall.

d) Elimination

The majority of the drug is not absorbed and is expelled in the feces. Orlistat's effectiveness in certain patient populations is unclear.

e) Pregnancy

Pregnant or nursing women should avoid using orlistat. It's a medication in the pregnancy category B.

f) Pediatric population

In the pediatric population, no study has been done to prove safety and effectiveness. Orlistat, on the other hand, has been demonstrated to be safe and beneficial in teenage obesity patients.

g) Renal impairment

In people with renal impairment, orlistat is safe.

h) Hepatobiliary

In individuals with clogged bile ducts and abnormal liver function tests, orlistat should be used with care.

E. ADVERSE EFFECTS

The following are some of the orlistat adverse effects:

a) Gastrointestinal

The most prevalent orlistat adverse effect is steatorrhea, which is caused by the reduced absorption of dietary fat. Fetal spotting, diarrhea, stomach discomfort, and anal fissures are some of the other negative symptoms. With continued orlistat medication, the gastrointestinal side effects diminish. These negative effects can be reduced by eating a hypocaloric, low-fat diet that contains fewer than 30% fat calories.

b) Renal

Orlistat has been linked to an increased risk of acute renal damage. This happens when unabsorbed fat interacts with calcium in the intestinal lumen, resulting in an excessive amount of oxalate being absorbed and deposited in the kidney, causing oxalate nephropathy and a higher risk of renal stones.

c) Musculoskeletal

Orlistat, in theory, can raise the risk of osteoporosis by impairing calcium and vitamin D absorption.

d) Cancer

Orlistat has been linked to an increased risk of colorectal cancer in animal studies. However, no such link has been discovered in people. Orlistat has been demonstrated to block the fatty acid synthase (Fas) enzyme's production, which promotes tumor development. In animal experiments, orlistat has been found to have anti-neoplastic effect in ovarian cancer cells, breast cancer cells, and prostate cancer cells.

F. DRUG INTERACTIONS

a) Antiepileptics

Orlistat can lower the plasma concentration of lipophilic antiepileptics such lamotrigine, valproate, vigabatrin, and gabapentin by reducing their absorption. Antiepileptic medication should be monitored in such circumstances. levels.

b) Amiodarone

Amiodarone absorption can be hampered by orlistat.

c) Cyclosporine

Orlistat can impair the absorption of cyclosporine (an immunosuppressant), it is recommended that these two drugs be given at least 2 hours apart. In addition, cyclosporine levels must be monitored in individuals who are on orlistat and cyclosporine.

d) Levothyroxine

Orlistat may bind to levothyroxine in the stomach and diminish its levels, resulting in a lower levothyroxine plasma concentration and hypothyroidism. As a result, doctors should urge patients to space their levothyroxine and orlistat doses by at least 4 hours.

e) Warfarin

When orlistat is used with warfarin, the prothrombin time might be extended. Because orlistat inhibits vitamin K absorption, it raises INR. As a result, coagulation occurs. In individuals who need to be monitored, these two drugs are administered jointly.

f) Antiretroviral medications

Orlistat also lowers antiretroviral medication absorption, necessitating HIV viral load monitoring. Orlistat should be stopped if the HIV viral load rises.

G. CONTRAINDICATIONS

The following conditions are contraindications to orlistat:

- Hypersensitivity to orlistat or its ingredients
- Cholestasis
- Chronic malabsorption
- Anorexia & bulimia(1)

H. SUBLINGUAL GLAND

Salivary glands, also known as sublingual glands, are located beneath the tongue in the floor of the mouth. They create mucin, which is then converted into saliva. The saliva produced by the glands keeps the interior of the mouth lubricated, which is important for chewing and food swallowing. Low saliva output can make it difficult to swallow meals, and the risk of food lodge in the throat rises. Absorption occurs when the medication is transferred from the site of injection into systemic circulation; hence, absorption is proportional to layer thickness. Because of its high permeability and abundant blood flow, the sublingual route can induce a quick beginning of effect, allowing for the administration of drugs with short delivery times and frequent dosing regimens. The medication is diluted in the saliva before being absorbed throughout the mouth cavity.

FIG. 1

I. SUBLINGUAL DRUG DELIVERY

"Systemic distribution of medications to the systemic circulation through the mucosal membranes lining the floor of the mouth." Sublingual drug administration is an alternative to enteral drug delivery. When a chemical comes into touch with the mucous membrane beneath the tongue, it diffuses through it because the connective tissue beneath the epithelium has a profusion of capillaries, and the material then diffuses into them and enters the venous circulation.

Drug solutes are absorbed quickly into the reticulated vein beneath the mouth mucosa, transported through the facial veins, internal jugular vein, and brachiocephalic vein, and subsequently reach systemic circulation.

FIG.2

J. ADVANTAGES OF SUBLINGUAL DRUG DELIVERY

- It has a rapid systemic impact because it allows the medicine to be absorbed fast or directly via the mouth's mucosal membrane beneath the tongue.
- The dose is lowered.
- The action begins quickly.
- Bioavailability has improved.
- There are fewer side effects.
- Necessary for diseases such as nausea, vomiting, migraines, and schizophrenia.
- There is no need to use water to give the pill.
- The ease with which drugs are administered improves.
- The sublingual region is far more porous than the buccal region.
- Bypassing the GI tract and the hepatic portal system, as well as avoiding hepatic first-pass metabolism, increases medication bioavailability.
- Rapid absorption due to high vascularization beneath the tongue. pH in the mouth is relatively neutral so drug will be more stable. Improved patient compliance.

CHAPTER 2

SUBLINGUAL FORMULATIONS

A. *Sublingual tablets*

Sublingual pills are solid unit dose forms that are placed beneath the tongue to provide rapid action by bypassing the liver's first pass impact." The tablets are typically tiny and flat, with a minimal compression to keep them supple. The API must be taken immediately, hence the pill must disintegrate quickly. It's made to dissolve in a minimal amount of saliva.

B. *Sublingual films*

The technology of the transdermal patch was used to make mouth dissolving films or strips, a novel drug delivery device for oral administration of medications. The delivery method consists of a very thin oral strip that is simply applied on the patient's tongue or any other oral mucosal tissue. When the film is moistened by saliva, it hydrates quickly and sticks to the application site. It then rapidly disintegrates and dissolves to release the drug for oromucosal absorption, or it can be modified to allow for gastrointestinal absorption when ingested. Sublingual strips are similar to tablets in that they dissolve quickly after being melted in the mouth.

C. *Multi-purpose tablets*

Hydrostat (hydromorphone) and a variety of brands of morphine tablets and cubes are soluble tablets for oral or sublingual delivery, typically also suited for preparation of injections.

D. *Sublingual drops*

As with certain nicocodeine cough treatments, concentrated solutions are to be dropped beneath the tongue.

E. *Sublingual sprays*

Certain human and veterinary medications are given as a spray for the tongue.

F. *Lozenges*

As with the Actiq fentanyl lozenge-on-a-stick, the effects of a metered and patient-controlled rate combination of sublingual, buccal, and oral delivery (lollipop).

G. *Effervescent sublingual tablets*

This approach accelerates the passage of the medicine via the mucosal membranes (as it does with carbonated or effervescent beverages in the stomach(2)

CHAPTER 3

THIN FILM SUBLINGUAL FORMULATIONS

Thin-film drug delivery employs a dissolving film or an oral medication strip to deliver pharmaceuticals to the small intestines as well as the mouth (buccally or sublingually) (enterically). A film is made with hydrophilic polymers that dissolve quickly on the tongue or in the buccal cavity, delivering the medication to the systemic circulation by dissolution when it comes into contact with fluids.

When compared to existing typical pharmacological delivery forms, thin films have the following advantages:

- In terms of increased bioavailability, superiority
- Patient compliance is high.
- Patents on active medicinal components are being extended.
- Non-invasive modes of administration make administration more convenient.
- Handling ease during production and transport
- In the creation of formulations, cost-effectiveness is important.

Formulations for buccal, sublingual, ophthalmic, and topical administration are some of the particular efforts in producing thin films. Thin films for delivering medication into the buccal or sublingual mucosa have gained a lot of attention in recent years.

CHAPTER 4

MATERIALS USED IN THE PREPARATION THIN FILMS

A. *Polymers*

They must be nontoxic, non-irritant, and free of leachable contaminants whether used alone or in combination to produce desired qualities. Water-soluble polymers are used to create a thin coating that disintegrates quickly, has strong mechanical strength, and has a pleasant mouthfeel.

The following polymers are typically used in thin film production:

- Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC)
- Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC)
- Hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC)
- Poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVP)
- Poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO)
- Pullulan
- Pectin
- Chitosan
- Sodium alginate
- Carrageenan
- Gelatin

Because a variety of polymers are available, thin films with specified qualities like weight, texture, solubility, strength, and stability may be developed.

B. *Plasticizers*

Plasticizer excipients include glycerol, propylene glycol, low molecular weight polyethylene glycols, phthalate derivatives such as dimethyl, diethyl, and dibutyl phthalate, citrate derivatives such as tributyl, triethyl, acetyl citrate, triacetin, and castor oil, and phthalate derivatives such as dimethyl, diethyl, and dibutyl phthal.

C. *Active pharmaceutical ingredients (API)*

Generally, 5%w/w to 30%w/w of active pharmaceutical ingredients can be incorporated in the oral strip.

D. *Stabilizing and thickening agent*

The stabilizing and thickening agents are used to increase the viscosity and consistency of the strip preparation solution or suspension before casting by increasing the viscosity and consistency of the dispersion or solution. All dosage forms, especially those carrying modest doses of extremely strong medications, must have drug content consistency.

CHAPTER 5

FACTORS AFFECTING ON SUBLINGUAL ABSORPTION

A. Solubility in salivary secretion

Aside from lipid solubility, the medication must also be soluble in aqueous buccal fluids, i.e., biphasic solubility is required for absorption.

B. Binding to oral mucosa

Drugs that bind to the oral mucosa are not widely available in the system.

C. pH & pKa of the saliva

The average pH of saliva is 6.0, which enhances the absorption of medications that are still bound together. Also, if the pKa is greater than 2 for an acid and less than 10 for a base, the medications are absorbed through the mouth mucosa.

D. lipophilicity of drug

Passive permeation requires a little higher lipid solubility than that required for GI absorption for a medication to be entirely absorbed through the sublingual route. (3)

CHAPTER 6

METHODOLOGY

A detailed literature search was conducted on published studies on the anti-obesity medicine "Orlistat," which is taken orally. Scientific databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed, and Science Direct were utilized to locate relevant publications and aid in the development of hypothetical assumptions.

As a result, we hypothesize that a thin film sublingual formulation of the anti-obesity medicine "Orlistat" will provide a more precise and rapid beginning of action than orally taken orlistat. Orlistat (xenical) is usually taken three times a day after a fatty meal in pill form. Thin films are thought to be a handy, easy-to-swallow, self-administrable, and quickly dissolving dosage form.

A. *methods of preparation of thin film sublingual formulations*

a) *Thin film drug delivery*

A thin layer of film Drug delivery is the method of releasing medications into the systemic circulation via a thin film that dissolves when it comes into contact with fluids. Dissolving films or strips disintegrate in one minute when placed in the mouth without drinking or chewing. This dissolving film or strips are intended to be placed under the tongue or inside the cheeks for oral delivery. This thin film melts quickly without the need of water. Plasticized hydrocolloids are commonly used in fast-dissolving films. (4)

The following are the many ways for creating oral thin films:

- casting & drying: (a) solvent casting (b) semi-solid casting
- Extrusion: (a) hot melt extrusion (b) solid dispersion extrusion
- Rolling method

b) *Casting & Drying*

a. Solvent -casting method

The oral film is made using the solvent-extraction method, in which water-soluble components are dissolved to generate a clear viscous solution. The pharmacologically active component and other agents are dissolved and mixed with bulk in a small amount of solution. The solution is then put into an aqueous solution. Remove any trapped air and cast the solution into film, which is then dried and cut into the desired sizes.

b. Semi-solid casting

A solution of water-soluble film forming polymer is first created using the semi-solid casting technique. The resulting solution is then combined with an insoluble polymer made from sodium or ammonium hydroxide, such as cellulose acetate butyrate, cellulose acetate phthalate, or cellulose acetate phthalate. After that, add the appropriate amount of plasticizer to produce gel mass. Finally, the gel mass is molded into films using heat-controlled drums. The thickness of the film is around an inch.

c) *Extrusion*

a. Hot melt extrusion

Extrusion of granules, sustained-release tablets, and transdermal and transmucosal drug delivery devices is a frequent procedure. Heat is used to mould a polymer into a film in this method of film processing. The drug carrier mix that has been placed into the hopper is conveyed, mixed, and melted by the extruder. To create chlorpheniramine maleate films, the melt is colour moulded into the appropriate film shape using a hot melt extrusion process.

b. Solid dispersion extrusion

The drug is first dissolved in a suitable liquid solvent before being incorporated into a PEG melt at temperatures below 70°C in this method. The solvent or drug selected may not be miscible with PEG melt, and the solvent may change the polymorphic form of drug precipitated in solid dispersion.

d) *Rolling Method*

Preparation of a premix, addition of active, and production of the film are all part of the rolling process. Except for the API, which is introduced to the master batch feed tank, the pre-mix batch comprises film forming polymer, polar solvent, and other components. The first metering pump and control valve then feed a predefined quantity of the master batch. In the mixer, the needed amount of medicine is added, and the combination is thoroughly combined to generate a homogenized matrix. The second metering pump feeds a predetermined amount of matrix into the pan. The metering roller determined the film thickness. Finally, the film is created on the substrate and removed by the support roller. (5)

B. QUALITY CONTROL TEST FOR FILM

a) Tensile strength

The amount of stress applied to a point where the film sample breaks is referred to as tensile strength. It's computed by dividing the applied load at rupture by the film's cross-sectional area, as shown below.

$$\text{Tensile strength} = \text{Load at failure} \times 100 / \text{Film thickness} \times \text{film width.}$$

b) Percent elongation

When a film sample is stressed, it stretches, which is referred to as strain. Strain is defined as the distortion of a film divided by the sample's initial shape. The stretching of the film rises as the material grows.

$$\text{Percent Elongation} = [(L-L_0)/L_0] \times 100$$

Where, L = Increase in length of film.

L₀ = Initial length of film.

c) Young's modulus

Young's modulus, commonly known as elastic modulus, is a measurement of a film's stiffness. It's the ratio of stress applied over the elastic deformation's strain zone.

$$\text{Young's Modulus} = \text{Slope} \times 100 / \text{Film thickness.}$$

d) Folding endurance

The film's folding durability is determined by folding it in the same location until it breaks. The number of times the film can be folded without breaking is known as the folding endurance value.

e) Thickness

A screw gauge is used to determine the thickness of the film. Using a regular approach, the thicknesses of six distinct places are measured.

f) Uniformity of drug content

In a volumetric flask, the 11 cm² film was sliced and dissolved in 6.8 phosphate buffer solution to produce up to 100 ml. The solution was then taken out and diluted to 10 ml with 1 ml. Using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer, the maximum absorption of the solution was measured, and the concentration was determined.

g) In-vitro disintegration time

The disintegration time is measured by swirling a glass of 25 mL distilled water every 10 seconds to see when the film begins to dissolve or break.

h) In-vitro dissolution studies

Standard basket or paddle apparatus as described in the USP pharmacopoeia can be used to study dissolution investigations. Dissolution medium: 900 mL stimulated salivary fluid (pH 6.4) at 50 rpm. Maintain a temperature of 37.0°C. At every 4-minute interval, 5 ml of sample is removed and replaced with 5 ml of new medium. Using a UV-Visible Spectrophotometer, the samples were diluted properly and spectrophotometrically measured at max.

i) Pharmacokinetic data analysis & bio availability evaluation

Rabbits are one of the few laboratory animals without keratinized mucosa, and their sublingual mucosal tissue is quite similar to that of humans. Plasma data may be used to determine the maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}) and the time it takes to reach that concentration (T_{max}). Using the trapezoidal rule, the area under the plasma concentration curve (AUC) and bioavailability may be estimated. (6)

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSION

The intervention in the intended paper was in the sphere of pharmaceutical preparation. We are examining the fact that the orlistat medicine, which is used to treat obesity and is taken orally, does not give adequate results. Obesity has become a worldwide issue of worrisome proportions in the last 20 years. According to the World Health Organization, there are approximately 400 million obese and 1.6 billion overweight individuals worldwide, with that number expected to nearly double by 2015. This is not a sickness that just affects adults; in 2005, at least 20 million children under the age of five were overweight. Gastrointestinal disturbances, steatorrhea, bloating, oily spotting, fecal urgency, and fecal unpleasantness are the most prevalent side effects of Orlistat, which is taken orally.

Assume that orlistat delivered through sublingual method is more effective than orlistat delivered orally. Because oral thin films have advantages over oral tablets, such as simplicity of administration, greater bioavailability, portability, preventing GI side effects, and enhancing patient compliance, we switched the orlistat pill to a rapid dissolving oral thin film dosage form. Because they are afraid of choking, most patients refuse to take solid dose forms. This technology provides a strong foundation for developing patent-free items and extending the patent life-cycle of current products. Rapid dissolving oral thin films are used in a variety of applications, including gastroretentive and sublingual administration systems, in addition to buccal fast dissolving systems.

A unique medication delivery technology is a quick dissolving oral thin film dosage form. Thin film drug delivery employs a dissolving film or an oral medication strip to deliver pharmaceuticals to the small intestines as well as the mouth (buccally or sublingually) (enterically). A film is made up of hydrophilic polymers that dissolve quickly on the tongue or in the buccal cavity, allowing the medicine to enter the systemic circulation immediately by dissolution when it comes into contact with fluids. As a result, a fast-dissolving oral thin film administered via the sublingual route is effective since the % of medication absorbed is often higher than that attained via the oral route.

Although this is only a hypothesis, no scientific investigation is required to assess the drug's safety and efficacy when administered sublingually. (7)

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